

Dynamic Differential Delay Aware RMSA for Elastic Multi-path Provisioning in GMPLS Flexi-grid DWDM Networks

R. Muñoz¹, R. Vilalta¹, M. Svaluto Moreolo¹, J.M. Fàbrega¹, R. Casellas¹, F.J. Vilchez¹, R. Martínez¹,
S. Frigerio², A. Lometti²

¹Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss n7, 08860 Castelldefels, Spain

²Alcatel Lucent Italia, Via Trento 30, 20871 Vimercate, Italy.
{raul.munoz}@cttc.es, {silvano.frigerio}@alcatel-lucent.com

Abstract: We experimentally evaluate multi-path RMSA algorithms that minimize the differential delay and the required buffer capacity. A proof-of-concept of multi-path routing, provisioning and transmission with a GMPLS-controlled Flexi-grid DWDM setup using S-BVTs is also presented.

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1. Introduction

In Flexi-grid DWDM networks, the spectrum is fragmented as the optical connections are dynamically established and released, thus it is quite likely that no continuous optical spectrum (i.e., frequency slot) can be allocated to a connection request. This leads to increase the connection blocking probability. The spectrum fragmentation problem can be solved by executing, at regular intervals, a network re-optimization mechanism that forces to reroute and/or reassign the frequency slot of the existing optical connections in order to defragment the optical spectrum [1]. Since this mechanism is very complex and intrusive, the frequency of execution should be rather low. Another alternative to minimize this problem is to split the traffic demand into multiple flows which can be routed via multiple independent paths, as proposed in [2] by the authors, combining the flexible capacity coming from the new concept of sliceable BVTs (S-BVT) [3] and the inverse-multiplexing techniques for OTN to exploit such flexibility. On the one hand, a S-BVT support the generation of multiple optical flows with different modulation formats and bit-rates (e.g., a 400Gb/s transceiver can be sliced in three virtual transceivers at 100Gb/s, 100Gb/s and 200Gb/s). On the other hand, though the OTN standard [4] primarily deals with the multiplexing of lower rate into higher rate signals, inverse-multiplexing is typically considered as well. Thus it is reasonable to assume that the new frame structure under discussion inside ITU-T for the evolution of the hierarchy beyond 100G would allow the segmentation of fat line interfaces in thinner pipes (e.g., in step of 100G). An attractive option, among others, is the so called ODUCn/OTUCn achieved interleaving 'n' 100G basic frames in an SDH-like manner. Thus, when there is not a contiguous portion of spectrum sufficient for the entire bandwidth, the OTUCn signal (made up of 'n' basic frames) could easily be distributed across 'm' (independent) media channels which can be either co-routed inside the same fiber/cable or diversely routed. For example, a 400Gb/s flow could be inversely multiplexed into two OTUC2 (200G) or one OTUC3 (300G) plus one OTUC1 (100G), or even four OTUC1 (100G), as shown in Fig.1.a. Thus, this technique can increase the number of served connection requests. However, the main drawback is the differential delay, caused when a traffic demand is routed via multiple paths that are not transported into the same fiber/cable. The differential delay is defined as the difference between the longest and the shortest path delay. It causes the need of deploying high-speed buffers at the terminating OTN equipment to store the data from the shortest paths until the longest path reach the destination, in order to synchronize the reception of all paths. In this paper, we propose and experimentally evaluate novel differential delay aware RMSA algorithms for elastic multi-path provisioning in GMPLS Flexi-grid DWDM networks in order to quantify the tradeoff between the increase of the served connections and the need of buffer capacity. We also present a proof-of-concept of an experimental multi-path provisioning and transmission considering the GMPLS-controlled Flexi-grid DWDM network setup developed in the ADRENALINE testbed.

2. Considered GMPLS/PCE control plane architecture

Our control approach relies on a distributed GMPLS control plane with a stateless PCE for centralized and dedicated path computation (Fig.2.a). The PCE builds a local TED by sniffing the OSPF-TE TE LSA exchange (i.e., IGP Listener). We consider the dissemination of the status of the spectrum slots (nominal central frequencies - NCF) as well as the availability of frequency slots on a per TE link basis. We introduce two new elements in the proposed architecture, namely, the inverse-multiplexing connection controller (IMCC) and the inverse-multiplexing provisioning manager (IMPM). The IMCC is responsible for the splitting of the requested OTUCn bandwidth into m sub-bandwidths and route them into one or multiple paths. The PCE is responsible for synchronously computing a set of elastic paths (i.e., spatial path, modulation parameters and spectrum allocation) for each one of the m sub-bandwidths considered by the IMCC. Finally, the IMPM is responsible for the synchronized provisioning of the multiple elastic paths, one for each sub-bandwidth, in a Flexi-grid DWDM network. Further details about the considered architecture can be found in [2].

Fig. 1 (a) Bandwidth splitting for OTUC2, OTUC3 and OTUC4. Routing of an OTUC4 using: (b) a single path and frequency slot, (c) multiple paths that are co-routed in the same fiber, (d) multiple paths that are diversely routed.

3. Differential delay aware multi-path algorithms

We propose three algorithms to serve the incoming OTUCn connection requests between a source (s) and a destination (d) node. The first two algorithms only consider path solutions with zero differential delay, whilst the third one, selects path solutions which minimize the differential delay. The first algorithm (Fig. 1.b), named *single-path* (SP), routes all the OTUC1 basic frames of an OTUCn connection through a single path (step 1). The second algorithm (Fig. 1.c), named *multi-path co-routed* (MPCR), additionally to SP, routes the OTUC1 components of an OTUCn through multiple paths co-routed in the same fiber (steps 1, 2 and 3). Finally, the third algorithm (Fig. 1.d), named *multi-path diversely-routed* (MPDR), additionally to MPCR, routes the OTUC1 components of an OTUCn through multiple diversely routed paths with the minimum differential delay (steps 1, 2, 3 and 4):

- *Step 1:* The IMCC requests to the PCE an elastic path (i.e., spatial path, modulation parameters and spectrum allocation) between s and d , considering the whole bandwidth of the OTUCn connection. The PCE executes the proposed combined RMSA algorithm described in Sec. 4. If the PCE can find a solution, the computed path information is sent to the IMPM for the connection provisioning. If no path exists, the connection request is blocked for the SP algorithm. For the MPCR and MPDR algorithms, go to step 2.
- *Step 2:* The IMCC splits the OTUCn bandwidth into m sub-bandwidths (Fig.1.a. provides an example of the bandwidth splitting for OTUC2, OTUC3 and OTUC4, with a granularity of OTUC1). If the requested bandwidth cannot be split (i.e., the requested bandwidth is OTUC1), the connection request is blocked.
- *Step 3:* The IMCC iteratively requests to the PCE (starting from $m=2$ to $m=n$) the synchronized computation of a set of paths, one for each sub-bandwidth, between s and d with the data rate of the sub-bandwidth, until it finds a solution where the computed paths have the same spatial path (nodes and links). If so, the IMCC passes to the IMPM the information about all the computed paths in order to perform a multi-path provisioning. If no path exists, the connection request is blocked for the MPCR algorithm. For the MPDR algorithm, go to step 4.
- *Step 4:* The IMCC iteratively requests to the PCE (starting from $m=2$ to $m=n$) the synchronized computation of a set of paths, one for each sub-bandwidth, between s and d with the data rate of the sub-bandwidth. From the set of available solutions, the IMCC computes the differential delay for each solution. Then, the IMCC selects the multi-path solution with the lower differential delay and computes the required buffer capacity. The delay of a path is computed by multiplying the end-to-end distance of the path (in km) by $5\mu\text{s}/\text{km}$. The required buffer capacity (in bits) is computed by multiplying the differential delay of each path by its data rate.

4. Combined PCE-based RMSA algorithm

First, it is performed an off-line transmission characterization of different paths (e.g., K-shortest path) across the network via simulation, considering the fiber impairments and filtering effects, as proposed in [5]. The output is a transmission table stored in the PCE that assigns the modulation parameters (modulation format, symbol rate, FEC, required optical spectrum, etc.) in function of the bitrate, path distance and hop count. We define a combined RMSA algorithm based on a constrained shortest path first (CSPF) algorithm using detailed per TE link information (i.e., status of the NCF). The CSPF algorithm computes the shortest hop-count path that satisfies the spectrum continuity constraint for a required amount of optical spectrum (i.e., frequency slot width). To estimate the necessary optical spectrum, the PCE follows an iterative approach. First, the PCE assumes the optical spectrum required by the most efficient modulation format considered in the pre-cached transmission table. Once the spatial path (i.e., nodes and links) is computed, the PCE performs a transmission table lookup to assign the most optimal modulation parameters (modulation format, symbol rate, FEC, required optical spectrum, etc.) in function of the distance and hop count of the computed path. In our approach, the physical link distance is stored in the extended TED. If the path was not feasible from a distance/hop-count perspective, the path computation is iteratively repeated with a less efficient modulation format until a solution is found. If no path is found, the path request is blocked. Finally, the last step is the assignment of the frequency slot (i.e., spectrum). From the available continuous frequency ranges in the computed spatial path, the PCE selects the first frequency slot available based on the required optical spectrum.

5. Experimental performance evaluation

Fig. 2.a shows the network topology of the GMPLS-controlled Flexi-grid DWDM setup employed in the proof-of-concept experimentation. In the considered test, when the IMCC receives a bandwidth connection request from the

Fig. 2 (a) Experimental network setup in the ADRENALINE testbed. (b) Sliceable BVT architecture. (c) Wireshark capture showing the exchange of control messages between the IMCC-IMPMM and the PCE and ROADM1. (d) Reference network topology for performance evaluation in the GMPLS/PCE control plane testbed. Total load vs (e) Total served connections, (f) Differential Delay and (g) Buffer capacity.

NMS, it requests to the PCE a single path to serve the requested bandwidth (Step 1 in Fig. 2.a and Fig. 2.c). Since the PCE cannot find a path (2), the IMCC splits the bandwidth into two sub-bandwidths, using either MPCR or MPDR, and requests to the PCE the computation of the two paths (3). The PCE can find a solution, and replies to the IMCC (4) with the full path information (spatial path, modulation parameters, etc). Then, the IMPM requests the provisioning of the two elastic paths to the head-end node of the paths (i.e., ROADM-1) using a TCP/XML interface (5,7). The elastic paths are provisioning by the GMPLS control plane. Once provisioned, the head-end node notifies to the IMPM (6,8). A proof of the multi-path transmission has been also performed using an S-BVT based on OFDM technology [6] (Fig.2.b). The data is split into two flows (Fig.2.a), consisting of two optical OFDM signals, which are generated using two tunable laser (TL) sources at $\lambda_1=1550.12\text{nm}$ and $\lambda_2=1550.92\text{nm}$. Low-complex off-line digital signal processing (DSP) is performed at the sliceable transmitter (S-BVTx), selecting BPSK format [6]. The digital signal, with electrical bandwidth of 5GHz, is converted to analog by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) at 12GSa/s. The optoelectronic front-end uses a single MZM, thus two identical signals at 5Gb/s, with 11GHz optical bandwidth, are generated. At the first node (ROADM-1), they are filtered and sent towards the same destination node (OXC-1) through two different optical paths: a single hop of 35km and a 2 hops path of 185km, respectively. Both signals have been successfully received using a PIN photodetector and a transimpedance amplifier (TIA), after optically filtering at 12.5GHz. The analog signal is captured by a real-time oscilloscope (DPO) at 50GSa/s and processed off-line using Matlab code. The BER performance has been evaluated at a target value of 10^{-3} , considering a 7% FEC. The measured receiver power at the destination node is -11.9dBm after 35km and -10.8dBm after the path of 185km, presenting about only 1dB penalty with respect to the signal at λ_2 .

The experimental performance evaluation of the proposed differential delay aware RMSA algorithms has been carried out in the GMPLS/PCE control plane platform of the ADRENALINE testbed, emulating the 14-node Spanish network topology, with 128 NCF per link (Fig.2.d). We requested batches of 1000 connections (Poisson arrivals, exponential holding time), selecting nodes randomly from the set of distinct node pairs and bandwidth randomly from 100 to 400Gbps. We have evaluated the total served connection requests (Fig.2.e), showing that multi-path algorithms (i.e., both MPCR and MPDR) outperforms the single-path algorithm (SP). MPCR has a more moderate improvement in comparison with MPDR, but this solution does not require the use of high-speed buffers. For MPDR, we measured the average, min. and max. differential delay (Fig.2.f) and the required buffer capacity (Fig.2.g). It showed an average differential delay around 2ms, and a buffer capacity slightly lower than 50Mbytes.

5. Conclusions

We have assessed the benefits of multi-path algorithms in Flexi-grid DWDM networks, even without the need of high-speed buffers. We have also shown that the required buffer capacity is rather low and it can be affordable.

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7. References

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